

Solid Waste Management in India

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Abstract

India is a developing nation growing at a very fast pace on the world platform. The growth in industrialization, urbanization and the overgrowing population has caused waste generation. Resultantly, the waste production is rising at an alarming state. The organic waste has reduced and inorganic waste has increase manifold. The wastes produced from households, hospitals, industries, contaminate air, water, soil and other resources. This paper attempts to study the reasons causing waste mis-management and relatively a preferable people friendly solution to this very cause.

Keywords

Organic, Alarming, Industrialisation, Mis-management, Growth, Platform.

Introduction

Humans depend on nature for his needs. Therefore, the resources are obtained from underground earth, forests, soil, water to satisfy his requirements. With the improvements in the living standards of people, the usage of ultra modern products has increased to provide comfort to his living. Rapid rise in industrialisation, urbanization has led to tremendous increase in inorganic waste materials like metals, glass, plastic, steel, medical instruments, demolition waste, biomedical waste in the form of drugs, sanitary pads, tissues and organs from healthcare facilities, electronic equipments, toxic industrial waste. These kind of inorganic constituents have led to increased amounts of solid waste which cannot be treated. The Nature, who provides the needed resources can't consume the waste produced by man. India, being the 2nd populous country with 17.5% of the world's population needs to find an intensive solution to this problem of management of waste material causing no harm to the environment,

The oldest method used for waste management is landfill method. It has been used to manage waste since man learnt about managing waste from his own nest or living area. The other cultivated method to treat waste is recycling method with the advancement in technologies.

Solid waste management refers to the storage and disposal process for solid wastes. The method adopted other than landfill method is the controversial method; incineration which leads to gaseous pollutants production. The municipal solid waste (MSW) is divided into six categories: food residues, wood waste, pulp, textiles, plastic and rubber. Solid waste treatment main elements include on- side management, processing and storing, garbage collection, waste management transfer and transport, reduction and final disposal.

Objective of study

1. To study the waste management systems efficiency in India.
2. To study the innovation in the disposal segment.
3. To study the public perception regarding solid waste management.
4. To analyze the economic, social and population indicators contributing towards waste amount and its collection.
5. To study the different methods adopted for waste collection.

Review of Literature

Katkar (2012) In this research article, techniques to optimise the solid waste collection. The study emphasizes that the total cost is spent mainly on the waste collection. So, the routes of collection can be cut short to have less costs. Minimal spanning tree technique is used to locate the shortest possible routes to collect waste from all dustbins in the study region.

Markovic (2010), This research paper focuses on the optimal solid waste management system in the city of NIS in Siberia. The system to collect the waste focuses on maximum system efficiency. A detailed measurement of waste is done on the site itself. It has adopted clarke-wright savings algorithm and the Geographical Information System.

Kumar and God (2009), did a case study in Kharagpur, west Bengal on the adopted management practices for integrated did waste management plan. In this study, it was found that most of the waste was dumped on open land contaminating found water. And the condition of community bins, collection vehicles is very poor. So composting can help divert more than 80% of the total waste.

Hazra and Goel (2009), did a case study in Kolkata. Collection of more than 2920 for of solid waste everyday makes it a tedious job. Lack of suitable facilities and

mismanagement causes problems in poor collection and transportation of municipal solid waste.

Main Text

Solid Waste Management in India: In India, the average solid waste generation per person per day varies depending on the city size. Small cities and towns generate around 0.1 kg per capita per day, while medium and large cities generate 0.3-0.4 kg and 0.5 kg per capita per day, respectively, according to Cpcb envis.

Solid Waste Management in India is a critical issue driven by rapid urbanization, growing populations and shifting consumption patterns. According to the Central Pollution Control Board's (CPCB) latest report, India generates approximately 160, 038 tonnes of solid waste daily. However, only about 50% of this waste is treated, with the remaining portion often ending up in the landfills or disposed of improperly, leading to environmental degradation and public health concerns. This situation highlights the urgent need for an efficient waste management system that can address India's escalating waste crisis in sustainable and effective way.

The current rate of solid waste generation in India stands at 0.34 kg per person per day, and it is projected to increase to 0.7 kg per person per day by the year 2025. By that time India is anticipated to surpass Germany, Japan and Brazil, which currently hold the 4th, 5th and 6th positions, respectively in terms of waste generation.

The Central Pollution Control Board, along with State Pollution Control Boards and committees, formulates environmental policies and oversees pollution monitoring and reporting at both the central and state levels. At the local level, municipal agencies and cantonment boards are responsible for implementing plans and regulations within their jurisdictions. They are tasked with developing infrastructure for the collection, segregation, transportation, storage, treatment, processing and disposal of solid waste. India's SWM rules mandate that citizens segregate waste at the household level and strictly avoid littering streets, ensuring waste is delivered through the systems established by civic bodies. Although India's SWM model was initially basic, the recent incorporations of concepts such as reduction, reuse and recycling (3R), along with material and energy recovery, has significantly enhanced the model.

Considering, state wise solid waste generation out of 28 states and 8 union territories (UT) of India, about 50% of solid waste is generated by only five States/UT -Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Gujarat and NCT of Delhi. Maharashtra with 23000 tons per day of solid waste stands at the top, followed by Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal with SWG of about 15,000 tons per day each. States such as Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Gujarat, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu create more than 10,000 TPD.

Maharashtra generates the highest amount of solid waste of all states and collects 99.3% of its solid waste. It utilizes 53% of the collected waste for composting, recycling and energy, recovery About, 47% of waste is sent to landfills. Arunachal Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Karnataka, Manipur, Nagaland and Puducherry collected 80% of the solid waste generated and treated only 25% of waste.

1. Delhi generates a large amount of waste, with estimates around 11,000 TPD.
2. Mumbai produces around 6,200 TPD.
3. Bengaluru contributes around 5,500 TPD.
4. Chennai's waste generation is also substantial, with 5475 TPD.

In India, urban areas generate significantly more waste than rural areas. Urban India produces about 42 million tons of municipal solid waste annually, while rural areas have a lower amount of waste. Urban India generates approximately 1.15 lakh metric tons of waste per day i.e 115,000 TPD.

Waste composition: The composition of solid waste in India differs from those found in western countries. On the net-weight basis, the physical composition of India's solid waste comprises of:

- (a) Biodegradable organic matter accounting for 51.3 ± 8.3%,
- (b) Recyclable constituting up to 17.48±5%,
- (c) Ash content ranging from 30-40%,
- (d) Paper making up about 3-6% and
- (e) Inert materials such as glass, plastic and metals comprising up to 1-6%.

Organic waste primarily consists of food and other biodegradable materials, while recyclables include items like paper, plastic, and metal.

However, due to inadequate segregation at the source, these materials often get mixed, making the process of recycling or composting more difficult and costly. This issue, compounded by a lack of awareness and motivation for waste segregation at the household level, poses a significant barrier to effective waste management of India.

Waste processing:

Waste processing comprises six steps-

1. Generation of waste
2. Storage of waste
3. Collection of waste
4. Transportation of waste
5. Process of segregation

6. Disposal of waste

Solid waste collection steps-

1. Door to door collection
2. Community collection centres
3. From community collection centres; the waste is sent to recycling or reuse centres and then lastly to disposal sites.
4. From community collection centres, the solid waste which needs not to be recycled is directly sent to disposal sites.

Waste Processing Method:

1. Waste is minimized, recycled and reused adopting several methods. At the first instance, the rag pickers collect metals, plastics, glass, leather items etc. Many people sell the recyclable items to waste buyers. And, then lastly to the waste dealers known as kabadiwallas, these send the recyclable items to recycling centres to make a new product. On an average, about 51% of the waste collected in India is minimized, recycled and reused. With the establishment of recycling units, the landfills are no more required. According to the reports of Central Board of Pollution Control the states like Jharkhand, U.P, Goa, West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh and Chhattisgarh recycle more than 90% of the waste collected. And, states like Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Manipur, Andaman and Nicobar Islands recycle just over 50% of the waste. The lowest amounts of recycling is done in Haryana, Gujarat, Daman and Diu, Meghalaya Puducherry and Odisha. But, recycling is a very dirty and unhygiene process to be processed.
2. Collection storage and segregation of waste- For collection of the garbage, metal containers with colour codes to help segregation of solid waste i.e. green containers for biodegradable waste and blue containers for non-biodegradable wastes. The municipal workers provide door to door service for collecting garbage and transport of waste to disposal sites by dumpers. As, being reported most of the cities fail to collect around 20% of their solid waste. Cities such as Mumbai, Delhi and Hyderabad collect more than 90% of their solid waste.
3. Transport and transfer- Transportation of the waste constitutes significant part of municipal expenditure methods of transportation can be trucks, trailers, mini dumpers, loaders in urban areas and carts in rural areas depending on the types of collection points. The rate of waste transportation is Rs. 800 per ton in India. Therefore, to cut down costs, proper waste disposal routes should be designed.
4. Treatment and disposal- For disposal of the waste materials landfills are chosen like, Ghazipur and Bhalswa in Delhi, and Deonar in Mumbai. Landfills lack re-circulation system. These sites are worked upon by rag pickers, animals but as, they lack ventilation the emissions of greenhouse gases into the air and leachate into the water causes contamination of air, soil, water altogether.
5. Key challenges and solutions to solid waste management in India- India's solid waste management faces several challenges which need to be managed by citizens and state level to cut down the constraints.

1. Inadequate Infrastructure-

Lack of collection and transportation results in piling up of waste without being dumped or reused.

Limited landfill space- No Landfills are left with open capacity.

Inadequate Treatment facilities- no facilities for processing and recycling waste.

2. Improper Waste Management Practices-

Lack of segregation at source. At the point of generation, no waste is segregated into biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste.

Unscientific disposal- landfill dumping and Incineration causes problems and pollutes air, soil and water collectively.

3. Financial constraints-

Limited budgets

Public-Private Partnership Challenges- they relatively face challenges related to finance and scope is not defined.

4. Public Awareness and Participation-

Low awareness among people for waste segregation and waste management practices.

Lack of motivation among citizens to surface the problem and deal with it.

5. Rising waste generation-

Population growth and urbanization is taking place in India at an alarming rate and this has led to surge in waste generation being difficult to be managed.

E-waste - with the rising technical growth, the e-waste production is increasing but, it's disposal is difficult to be managed.

6. Policy implementation-

The implementation of the policies related the waste management is quite difficult to be managed.

7.Greenhouse Gas Emissions-

Landfills are the major contribution of methane emissions. Therefore, landfills are the untapped source of potential energy.

8. Health issues-

The solid waste includes plastics, chemicals, electronics, household wastes, construction wastes. And, these are all carcinogenic in nature leading to cancer, renal, kidney problems with major impact on the nervous system of the human body.

Solution to key challenges- Humans are the ones who are known as Homo sapiens with inborn intellect and intelligence. So, they can decide and take measures for their better future. Therefore, Awareness is the key to waste management. Hence, govt. policy, laws and financial approval for the programmes can be fruitful to manage this issue. The key factor to manage this cause at root level is to deal with segregation of waste at primary level of door to door collection.

Instead of using incineration and Landfilling, methods such as composting can reduce GHG emissions.

Recycling of maximum solid waste materials should be encouraged.

GIS based waste disposal routes should be designed.

Techniques such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, computer vision methods should be employed for automated identification and segregation of waste.

Conclusion

Solid waste management should be treated as an energy option for the contemporary society. It fulfills the criteria to satisfy the increasing population energy needs. Therefore, awareness, training, education, planning, policy formulation, effective management for collection generation, minimization storage, transport, treatment, recycling and disposal. Following these methods can bring fruitful results for the humanity to sustain and live in natural conditions with high productivity levels.

References

1. T.J. Sin, G.K. Chen, K.S. Long, I. Goh, and H. Hwang, "Current practice of waste management system in Malaysia : Towards sustainable waste management," *Ist FPTP Postgrad. Semin. "Towards Sustain. Manag.*, 2013.
2. A. Khalid, M. Arshad, M. Anjum, T. Mahmood, and L. Dawson, "The anaerobic digestion of solid organic waste," *Waste management*. 2011.
3. M.D.M. Samsudin and M.M. Don, "Municipal solid waste management in Malaysia: Current practices, challenges and prospect," *J. Tekno. Sciences Eng.*, 2013.
4. U, Arena, "Process and technological aspects of municipal solid waste gasification. A review," *Waste Manag.*, 2012.
5. Khajaria A, Matsui T. Machimura T. Economic growth decoupling-Kuznets curve: Symptom of the Decoupling in India. *J. Sustain. Dev.* 2011;4:51-8. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jsd.v4n3p51>.
6. Mor S. Ravindra K, De Visscher A. Dahiya RP, Chandra A. Municipal solid waste characterization and its assessment for potential methane generation: A case study. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2006;371:1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2006.04.014>.
7. Ganguly RK, Chakraborty SK. Integrated approach in municipal solid waste management in COVID-19 pandemic: Perspectives of developing country like India in a global scenario. *Case Stud. Chem. Environ. Eng.* 2021;3:100087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2021.100087>
8. <https://cleanindiajournal.com/india-to-generate-0-7kgwaste-per-person-per-day-by-2025-report/>